

World Experience Programming in Creating an Electronic Dictionary Website

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Article information:

Manuscript received: 4 Aug 2024; **Accepted:** 10 Sep 2024; **Published:** 07 Oct 2024

Abstract: In this article, we describe the essence, function and importance of the website in relation to our purpose. This website is intended to serve as a comprehensive resource for anyone interested in forestry, providing detailed information on a wide variety of plants and trees. The platform includes different species, each of which is listed with its scientific and common name, a brief description of its characteristics and a high-quality pictorial representation. Also, the website is available in 4 languages: Uzbek, English, Russian and German. With user-friendly navigation and visually appealing content, the website aims to promote the appreciation of biodiversity in forests and the green world, making it easy to explore the rich flora around us.

Keywords: Frontend (website design), backend (database), navigation panel, admin panel, search system.

Introduction

The modern world is developing so rapidly that people are not always aware of all its changes. We are creating new technologies and new trends to make our lives easier. Today, the 21st century is called the age of information technology, where the main product is information and how we present it. Similar questions have passed through many world experiences, and we can cite a few examples of them. Nowadays, we can safely say that computer programs have become a part of our daily life. We use them almost every day, even every hour, collecting information through them. Websites are created to help people with a specific purpose, so we can trust them. The goal is to offer a convenient and informative database for foresters, botanists, researchers, students, and nature lovers. Design, structure, and layout aspects of many electronic dictionaries were studied in the creation of our website, which we named "Multilingual Illustrative Electronic Dictionary of Terms Related to Forestry in Uzbekistan". In particular, the following dictionaries have been used to improve the knowledge skills of users based on world experiences.

Study of popular electronic dictionaries

The Cambridge Dictionary website is dedicated to providing accurate, up-to-date and easily accessible language resources to users around the world. It serves as a complete online dictionary for English language learners, native speakers, and professionals, and offers definitions, translations, synonyms, grammar tips, and pronunciation guides.

The main purpose of the **Oxford Dictionary** website is to provide authoritative and comprehensive definitions, meanings, and information about the English language. It serves as a reliable linguistic resource for students, scholars, professionals, and general users, providing insight into word origins, pronunciation, usage, and grammar. In addition to this, it not only allows you to follow the evolution of the language by constantly adding new words and updating meanings, reflecting changes in the language that adapts to social, technological, and cultural changes, but also learning tools, grammar tips, and supporting language learning by offering usage examples, helping users improve their language skills.

The main purpose of the **Duden Wörterbuch** website is to serve as an authoritative reference for the German language, providing comprehensive and accurate information on German vocabulary, grammar, spelling, and usage. It is widely accepted as the standard for the correct use of the German language in both written and spoken form. Like the Cambridge and Oxford dictionaries of the English language, Duden tracks changes in the language, regularly adding new words and meanings that appear in popular and official usage. In short, the main purpose of the Duden Wörterbuch website is to provide a clear guide to the correct use of the German language, to help keep up with new developments in the language, and maintain its linguistic standards.

Slovari i entsiklopedii na Akademike (Academic Dictionaries and Encyclopedias) aims to provide a comprehensive, multilingual online resource of dictionaries, encyclopedias, and reference books. The platform offers a wide range of knowledge in various fields. For example, the platform has a wide range of dictionaries, encyclopedias, and dictionaries on many subjects such as linguistics, science, history, and culture. It supports multilingual users, offers translations, definitions, and explanations in several major languages, and helps users access knowledge globally.

Studies show that the project will be completed in a short period of time and considering the large size of the database, it was concluded to create our own national site, which is not so complicated but does not cause difficulties for the user.

Advantages of electronic dictionary

In an era of technological advancement and growing environmental awareness, the importance of readily available, reliable information about plants and trees has always been paramount. An online dictionary dedicated to plants, trees, and the flora of nature in general offers many advantages that are useful for many users - from botanists and ecologists to gardeners and nature lovers. What are the main advantages of such a resource?

1. The online dictionary of plants and trees can be accessed anytime and anywhere, providing people with a world of knowledge. Whether you're doing research in the field, studying in the field, or using it to expand and strengthen your knowledge, an online resource can provide quick information without bulky books or hard-to-find manuals.
2. Unlike printed sources, online dictionaries can be continuously updated to reflect the latest scientific discoveries, classification changes, and newly discovered species. This ensures that users always have the most up-to-date and accurate information about plant species, their uses, habitats, and ecological roles.
3. The online dictionary's powerful search and filtering tools make it easy to find exactly what you're looking for. Users can search by plant name, species, region, or specific characteristics such as leaf shape, flower color, or growing conditions. This speeds up research and helps users find relevant information quickly.
4. In a world where many plant and tree species are threatened by deforestation, climate change, and habitat loss, an online dictionary can play an important role in raising

conservation awareness. It can educate the public about the importance of protecting endangered species and promoting biodiversity, thereby contributing to global conservation efforts.

Demonstration of the electronic dictionary website

Information from the scientific works of scientists dealing with the flora of Uzbekistan was used to create the database. The collected data were written in the Word text editor in alphabetical order. One of the experiences of the world is the work done by Japanese scientists on the creation of "multilingual forest terminology", and the Japanese experience was also studied.

Here we explain how to use the Multilingual Forest Terminology Database experimental system with screenshots showing the website. At the top when we enter a website, the Navbar or navigation bar is an interactive user element that has a menu or set of links to the main sections of the website. It is usually located at the top or side of a website and provides quick access to various pages.

Figure 1. Dictionary site navigation panel

This navigation panel has 3 pages that pull out information. The so-called main page of the navigation bar, that is, the homepage, is the main web page of the website. The term can also refer to the start page displayed in a web browser when an application is first opened. Since our website is available in 4 languages, the user can use any of the 4 languages. These languages include Uzbek, English, Russian and German.

On the main page, in the top part of the navigation panel, the video "youth in the bosom of nature" is placed, which appears as the design of the background part. In addition, the word search system is also located in this part.

A dictionary search engine is a software system that provides hyperlinks to web pages and other relevant information on the Internet in response to a user request. A user enters a query within a web browser or mobile app, and the search results are often a list of hyperlinks along with textual summaries and images. Users also have the option to limit their search to certain types of results, such as images, videos or news.

Figure 2. Dictionary search system

For a search provider, its engine is part of a distributed computing system that spans many data centers around the world. The speed and accuracy of the engine's query response is based on a complex indexing system that is constantly updated by automated web browsers. This may include data mining of files and databases stored on web servers, but some content cannot be accessed by browsers.

By way of reference, there have been many search engines since the advent of the Internet in the 1990s, but Google Search became dominant in the 2000s and has remained so. The business of websites improving their visibility in search results, known as marketing and optimization, is therefore primarily focused on Google [1].

As an example, let's give the word apple to the search engine.

Figure 3. System search image

In the next step, the result of the search given for information will be displayed. In this case, when the mouse is clicked on the word apple appearing in the picture, the other three names of the apple, i.e. English, Russian and German, appear in the button position.

Figure 4. View of the search result

All the information of the above-mentioned article fully discloses the working functions of the "search system".

Figure 5. Body part image

The next resource base is placed in the body part of the navigation bar, that is, the body element contains all the content of the HTML document, for example, headings, paragraphs, images, hyperlinks, tables, lists, etc.

There is a database in the admin part of the site, what is the database itself? A database is a systematic collection of information stored in electronic form. It can contain any type of data, including words, numbers, images, videos, and files. You can use software called a database management system to store, retrieve, and edit data. In this dictionary, you will be able to view words, pictures and, if necessary, videos as a database.

After the collected resources are edited and certain corrections are made, the process of placing the resources on the site begins. Placement of resources is carried out in several stages.

1. The administrator has the right to place the resource.
2. Log in to the system using a login and password. (If the login or password is incorrect and someone else is logged in instead of the administrator, they will be immediately redirected to the main page of the website and the operation will not be allowed).

Figure 6. Login image

3. After logging in to the admin, resources are placed by him using the "add word" button on the left side of the page. If there is a need to add comments, add information, insert some pictures and videos, it is done using the "edit" button. The "delete-delete" button is used to delete excessive and excessive data capacity or to completely remove the placed resource.

Figure 7. Enter information and *edit* and *delete* buttons in the right corner

Conclusion

The bottom line is that the Online Dictionary of Plants and Trees is a dynamic and invaluable tool for anyone interested in understanding the flora that surrounds us. Its quick access,

comprehensive content, and user-friendly features make it an essential resource in today's digital and environmentally conscious world. The website is constantly improved based on user requests and suggestions to improve its functionality and content. By proactively collecting feedback, the platform aims to meet the changing needs of its users, offering a more personalized, user-friendly experience. This collaborative approach ensures that new features, content updates, and improvements meet user expectations, making the website a more valuable and dynamic resource.

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